

Beyond the Hype: Rethinking Climate Change Narratives and Exploring Innovative Paths Toward a Sustainable Future

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Abstract

Various narratives can be relevant in explaining and creating awareness on global warming because they can help harmonize information from different actors. Different players present varying perspectives on efforts required to alleviate the impact of climate change. The publication and review of 64 papers aimed at critically examining and reassessing the discourse surrounding climate change to move beyond sensational and exaggerated claims, and explore innovative and forward-thinking approaches that contribute to achieving a sustainable future. The paper first highlights the question of how current climate change discourse contributes to public understanding by addressing traditional narratives surrounding climate change. It also addresses the potential drawbacks of sensationalism and traditional narrative. The paper also highlights ways that can explore a balanced narrative to positively impact public perception and engagement with climate-related issues. Still, the work explores whether there are examples of successful policy reforms or economic initiatives that have effectively contributed to a more environmental future in the light of climate change. The results indicate that traditional narratives are still dominating, and transformative narratives are far from being mainstream. Ideas and concepts revolve around mitigation, which the majority of literature works in advanced nations countries focus on. However, the paper also observes some transformative narratives and innovative pathways challenging traditional narratives. These innovative approaches can open the way for additional social creativity and a sustainable future. Most studies propose additional studies to further comprehend and evaluate these innovative pathways since various obstacles require unpacking to shed more light on the effects of these pathways and the general public.

Keywords: *Climate Change, Policy and Narrative, Talks and Claims, Mental Health, Cognitive Effects.*

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Introduction

Global warming and its consistent adverse impact pose severe risks to life in all regions of the globe. Due to the unfavorable implications of global warming, there is a need for global concern, mitigation efforts, and support for policies that would limit human activities contributing to climate change (Umegbolu, 2020). The term "climate change" refers to the perennial average changes in characteristics of the climate,

usually recorded over many years. The concept of "climate" denotes the long-term weather characteristics of a particular location. The continuous accumulation of atmospheric variables, such as temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, and their changes, is known as the climatic condition or state (Ani *et al.*, 2021; PHICCH 2016).

Moreover, the detrimental effects of climate change can be classified into economic, social, political, and physical environment, living things (plants and animals), and human health (Umegbolu, 2020). Focusing on health, the overall balance of climate change's effects would be adverse, given its effects on the environment, ecology, and society. The health effects of climate change will be felt more in low-economic nations and by the weak in wealthy nations. Due to changes in climatic conditions, the impact of global warming on health and general well-being is irregularly distributed around the world (Carleton and Hsiang, 2016).

The narrative may help improve the veracity of climate change communications by harmonizing the statements of various actors and players. It is worth noting that different players present diverse narratives on the mitigating actions to alleviate the significant impact of climate change. These narratives are portrayed in many ways, including as Legends, casualties, or antagonists (Bushell *et al.*, 2017). Communicating climate change policy is a complex phenomenon, owing to the independent interpretation of ideas by various groups. Such interpretations often lead to misunderstandings and confusion, which severely undermine the rationale for reform. (Schäfer and Hase, 2023).

The research on the dialect used during interactions and the talks around the effects of climate change have been ongoing since 2000. These analyses concentrated on various text and speech styles produced in diverse contexts by different voices, perspectives, and ideas (Dahl, 2021). Climate change consciousness has been a source of concern since 1988 when the Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) issued early conclusions. (Capstick *et al.*, 2015).

During the late 1990s, language-based approaches focused on researching climate connections by expanding on previous studies in psychology and sociology (Fløttum and Gjerstad, 2017). However, interaction is critical in this situation because information transmits and reflects emotions, while also influencing people's mindsets and behaviors. Information sharing helps individuals and groups to depict facts and give new views on the climate change subject. Moreover, it also addresses the complex debate on global warming by harmonizing the multiple voices from various players and objectives (Fløttum, 2016).

In creating and implementing social solutions to human-caused global warming, professionals must use efficient accounts, oral history, and environmentally friendly messaging (Moser, 2016). Stakeholders and decision-makers must engage within and beyond science on the subject through diverse media platforms, such as virtual media outlets, social networking sites, and rapid messaging (Segeberg, 2017; Walter *et al.*, 2019). In this regard, professionals have begun researching climate change communication strategies (Comfort and Park, 2018). The article seeks to critically examine and reassess the discourse surrounding climate change, moving beyond sensationalism and exaggerated claims, and exploring innovative and forward-thinking approaches that contribute to achieving a sustainable future.

Traditional Narratives on Climate Change

Traditional narratives are publicly produced stories and myths explaining the events and occurrences, and incorporating them into perspectives (van der Leeuw, 2019). These narratives influence human behavior by forming preferences and opinions (Fløttum and Gjerstad, 2017). As opposed to actual climate information, evidence shows that narratives determine whether or not climate change exists, and what should be done about it.

Examples of Traditional Narrative on Climate Change Involve

Top-down doom along with gloomy stories

The “top-down” approach involves reducing carbon projections and emissions to build a sustainable future. The past storyline on climate action has been the potential risk associated with the “top-down” approach of international Carbon abatement. The conventional understanding of scientific policy relations knowledge deficit paradigm and mainstream climate change research supports this claim this story (Simis *et al.*, 2016). Environmental studies can help authorities understand the impacts of emissions of greenhouse gases. In essence, today’s pollution may have severe influence on subsequent civilizations with more frequent serious climatic conditions. These severe climatic conditions include rising sea levels, and increased pressure on incomes, food production, and healthcare (IPCC, 2015). The investigation reveals that while industrialized nations and strong economies are the primary polluting entities, the consequences are typically felt in impoverished countries (Hinkel *et al.*, 2020).

Moreover, the story provides compelling moral grounds for eliminating climate gasses while supporting disadvantaged nations in covering the adapting financial expense. Still, some may claim that this narrative has been effective in raising the profile of climate change on the political horizon, as indicated by the setting up of UNFCCC (Hinkel *et al.*, 2020). Due to such tales, countries embarked on strong climate change mitigation objectives and created monetary movements in all nations to address the moral issues (Okereke and Coventry, 2016).

Nevertheless, the trend failed to establish a legally binding global accord on national emission reductions. The 2009 Copenhagen Conference of Parties exposed the fundamental faults in this scenario by failing to obtain such a universal accord since cutting emissions proved excessively costly, inefficient, and frustrating the national economic growth (Hinkel *et al.*, 2020).

The war against global warming creates societal conflicts since some countries benefit from others' costly carbon release (Nordhaus, 2019). As a result, the only viable approach to tackling the climate disaster is for countries to reduce the costs and amounts of carbon they emit. Nations must come together to develop a legally enforceable agreement that distributes national revenues to worldwide carbon emissions (Gollier and Tirole, 2017).

However, a new storyline emerged from the 2015 Paris Accord, focusing on national authorities' voluntary commitments to fight climate change, known as “Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).” The accord recognizes the challenging sacrifices nations could face in mitigating climate change and boosting their economies. Therefore, it focuses more on developing remedies that meet the demands of individual countries (Okereke and Coventry, 2016).

Despite the top-down approaches to climate change, the gloomy attitude remains pervasive in various aspects of climate policy, non-profit conversations, climate-related papers, and media coverage. The civil society's efforts to expose the lack of collaborative and democratic government in avoiding the “climatic problems,” also support the story (Rebellion, 2019). Even though climatologists differ on whether sharing negative statements on climate change might inspire positive action, other data suggest that doing so may hurt the campaign (Chapman *et al.*, 2017).

The Green Growth Narrative

The green growth narrative, also referred to as the green economic narrative, has also gained popularity in recent years. Since green development would solve the global public good, it has equal potential to solve the climate dilemma (Guerra *et al.*, 2021). Under the “green growth theory,” individual nations would be motivated to cut emissions to benefit economically and create a safe climate for everyone on the planet (Hickel and Kallis, 2020). That explains why the green growth concept has become popular in the field of policy. Leading international organizations, such as the International Labor Organization,

The UNEP, UNIDO (World Bank), and many Asian and Pacific authorities believe that an environmentally friendly economy is a potential growth model. The green growth vision improves overall health and social fairness while lowering ecological dangers and biological scarcity" (Adamowicz, 2022). The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number 8 seeks to separate growth in the economy and ecological deterioration and includes the green growth claim even more explicitly (UNDESA 2020).

Questions have risen on whether the carbon growth is achievable, or if the green growth is a mere catchphrase for development. Issues have also come up regarding the defined consequences of green growth on employment and its dispersal implications. However, research has shown that financial advancement is topically associated with greenhouses (Parrique et al., 2019). These findings support the narrative that carbon gas increase may not be successful in solving ecological dilapidation and health (Hickel and Kallis, 2020). Still, the same research underscores that there is little investigation on this issue, and very little support has been committed to the idea of using applied economic modeling and economic theory (Ward *et al.*, 2016).

Methods

The study employed a Cochrane review method to generate a more thorough collection of data on the issue. The approach allowed for a meticulous focus on the main areas of research, and an integration of the results. (Pollock *et al.*, 2020). Cochrane methods reduce biases during the review by identifying relevant studies from multiple sources (Pollock *et al.*, 2020).

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed after considering the research topic, objectives, and the variables at play.

- (1) How does the current climate change discourse contribute to public understanding, and what are the potential drawbacks of sensationalism in this narrative?
- (2) How might a more fair and complex narrative improve the public's understanding and involvement with climate-related troubles?
- (3) Are there any instances of fruitful policy reforms or commercial efforts that have helped to create a better tomorrow in the face of climate change?

Search Strategies and Evaluation Guidelines

The study employed a systematic search approach to find relevant studies. The study also employed two criteria for inclusion. The first criterion involved both original research or systematic reviews of original research, while the second one involved at least one narrative about climate change and its implications connected to climate change, directly or indirectly. The researchers used Google Scholar, and Science Direct to find the article, based on the title, time or publication keywords, and their relevance. Based on Cochrane's definition, systematic review is defined as an examination of the research to identify, evaluate, and synthesize every piece of data that satisfies predetermined eligibility criteria on a particular research question. The search involves the application of clear, organized methodologies that are chosen to reduce bias and generate more trustworthy results to guide the decision-making process (Hoffmeyer *et al.*, 2023). The researchers excluded grey literature, blog posts, and news. The researchers' definition of the significant effect of environmental degradation and its narrative focused on the IPPC. According to The World Health Organization, health refers to the whole mental, interpersonal, and physiological well-being rather than the mere lack of illness or injury. Below are some of the consequences of global warming on health.

Impacts of Climate Change on the Public

The fifth evaluation report of the Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) demonstrates the effects of environmental degradation resulting from increased warming temperatures. The IPCC states that local climatic changes, especially temperature rises, have already impacted a wide range of physical and biological systems worldwide. Climate change challenges sustainability because of its many possible repercussions. The impacts include detrimental effects on the general public, heat growth of the planet's outermost waters and condensing icebergs on land, leading to increase in sea levels, inundation, and agricultural erosion. Other impacts of climate change include the loss of crop territories, an increase in the acidity of reservoirs due to excess carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, and the entry of salt into inland water bodies, among others. (IPCC, 2015).

Factors, such as the global economy, infrastructure, energy, and health experience climate change's effects and its subsequent impact on humans (Di Napoli *et al.*, 2022). The current death toll from ecological and bad climate requires urgent concerns and solutions. According to data presented by Zhao *et al.* (2021), there are roughly five million deaths globally related to climate change. Additionally, by 2030 and 2050, the World Health Organization estimates an extra 250,000 fatalities in season (WHO, 2021). While the physical symptoms of the detrimental effects of environmental changes on health are all over the media, psychological factors are also vital to the health effects of climate change. Unfortunately, these specific effects are usually overlooked in both scientific research and the media since the emphasis is predominantly on the ecological and financial consequences of global warming (Lawrence *et al.*, 2021).

Mental Health Impact of Climate Change

According to the group being studied and individual differences, symptoms associated with psychological wellness and global warming manifest in different ways. Fortunately, a few consistent patterns can be discovered in scientific writing. According to Hau (2023), ecological anxiety is a phase of increased awareness of health threats caused by shifting weather and temperatures. This anxiety results from global warming, causing the onset of insomnia and excessive levels of worry. The authors also discuss the emotions of personal guilt associated with human-caused global warming, and the possibility of an existential threat to the Earth and humanity as a whole, creating increased stress levels (Hau, 2023). Natural calamities are also responsible for additional climate change's harmful impact on mental health. Psychological complications such as mental trauma and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) also affect individuals who have been directly affected by or dealing with the consequences of environmental disasters (Lawrence *et al.*, 2021). Cianconi *et al.* (2020) also discovered that continuous reading of negative news about climate change leads to escalating the symptoms of depressive disorders. The emergence of social media and other instant sources of news propagate global warming information daily, enhancing the consumption of negative news that could escalate psychological impacts on the public (Cianconi *et al.*, 2020).

It is equally essential to consider the growing coverage of climate change in the news and on online platforms in the past few years. A recent study on "environmental stress," depicts that many people feel worried when they think about the possibly fatal risk posed by climate change (Coffey *et al.*, 2021). The study also suggests that scientific reports show that adolescents and young adults are particularly affected by climate change nervousness, causing inadequate sleep, tension, nervousness, and rage (Coffey *et al.*, 2021).

Doom-scrolling

Doom-scrolling is the act of grabbing or reading shocking information from social media. The phenomenon has arisen primarily as a result of the increased consumption of negative news from social media and other news outlets. Studies suggest that some people intentionally seek unfavorable news and information on the internet and social media platforms (Anand *et al.*, 2022). Although mobile devices are

the most popular tech tools for doom scrolling, it may also entail watching a steady stream of depressing news headlines on television and video contents (Ytre-Arne and Moe, 2021). During the recent COVID-19 outbreak, the inclination to constantly search for "doom and gloom" on the internet and news stations has been explored. Hau (2023) showed a connection between teenage depression symptoms and the consumption of unfavorable information about the pandemic on social media.

Hau (2023) conducted a quantitative study and highlighted the detrimental impact that perceived negative knowledge of climate change causes on people's anxiety levels. The study's findings corroborate the earlier studies, suggesting that perceived negative news escalates anxiety levels. Before comparing this study with earlier research, it should be noted that the earlier experiments were primarily carried out with COVID-19 doomscrolling in mind. Sharma *et al.* (2022) and Satici *et al.* (2022) are some of the earlier studies that revealed an existing linkage between doomscrolling and poor mental well-being results.

A qualitative study by Apprich, (2023) also finds that the majority of participants experienced various forms of psychological discomfort after reading critical climate change news articles. Such individuals believe that hearing about critical climate change news makes them feel depressed, angry, or helpless. The findings correspond with previous studies on the impacts of impending doom on psychological well-being (Sharma et al., 2022) and the effects of global warming news reading (Cianconi et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the conflicted responses to the issues presented by climate change are consistent with earlier studies on the subject (Stollberg and Jonas, 2021). When considering doom-scrolling news consumption, it is essential to consider reported news avoidance, a reaction to the declining impact of doom-scrolling on mental health (Ytre-Arne and Moe, 2021). However, there is no prior research on climate change doomscrolling to compare the results.

Figure 1. Hypothesized Model on the Connection that Exists between Climate Change, Doomscrolling and HD
 Source: Apprich, 2023

The study's quantitative aspect demonstrates a strong correlation between climate change and doomscrolling, and resilience to HD and social support. However, the linear regression analysis with a controlling influence did not show any environmental change in the association between doom-scrolling

and feelings of no assistance and melancholy. Still, neither the association between doom-scrolling and HD nor the connection that exists between doom-scrolling, climate change and HD showed any moderation by social support (Fig. 1.). As a result, the analysis contradicts the following model of moderation hypothesis (Aprich, 2023).

Results

This section explains the various new transformative climate change narratives deemed necessary to discuss when analyzing and going through 64 journals and studies from the book.

Articles Identified

An inclusion criterion was employed to select 64 references from the initial 183 references. After scanning the titles and abstracts, 103 studies were available for the entire text examination. During the full-text inspection, 39 studies were excluded, as they failed to meet the relevance to the narrative or discourse on ecological change. Thirteen (n=13) were not related to climate change (n=11), while no retrievable full text (n=15).

Study Descriptions

The publication years ranged from 2015 to 2024 since the vast number of featured articles ranged from 2018 upwards. The keywords and relevant themes are summarized in Tab. 1 and Fig 2.

Table 1. Summary of Keywords

Literatures keywords	Theme	Number of papers
Climate change narratives	Climate change	7
Rethinking Climate change Narrative	Climate change discourse	9
Sustainable future on climate change storytelling	Climate change discourse	3
Innovative pathways to climate solutions	Climate change	10
Regenerative sustainability	Climate change	2
Green technology innovations	Climate change	4
Nature-based solutions for climate change	Climate change	2
Community-driven sustainability	Climate change policy	3
Policy advocacy for climate action	Climate change policy	6
Global collaboration on climate change	Climate change	7
interactive storytelling on climate issues	Climate change discourse	2
Social media challenges for sustainability	Climate change discourse	9

Figure 2. Summary of Keywords

Rethinking Climate Change Narrative

The Bottom-up Narrative

The new bottom-up narrative appears to be leading toward a sustainable future since climate action's opportunities and co-benefits are becoming more prominent. For instance, the European Commission (2019) suggested that Europe seeks to be the first continent globally to achieve carbon neutrality by the year 2050, unveiling a decision to raise a minimum of \$1 trillion in funding for the EGD (European Green Deal). However, there is still a substantial difference between the objectives to reduce national ecological warming to "less than 2°C". Furthermore, it is also unknown whether other nations will honor their voluntary agreements (Hickel and Kallis 2020).

Despite the transition from top-down to bottom-up approaches, inconsistencies continue to prevail in many aspects of environmental policy materials such as CBO discussions, climate research publications, and media coverage. However, many community-based organizations trying to explain the inadequacies of democratic and accountable government in averting the "environmental calamity," have also reignited interest in this topic. Moreover, there is proof that this may be ineffective in motivating conservation efforts around the subject. Hinkel et al. (2020) and climate researchers disagree on whether negative messaging about global warming will stimulate actions (Chapman et al., 2017).

The Degrowth Narrative

The decreasing story raises concerns on the long-term importance of ongoing financial expansion and claims that more crucial changes to the societal framework. The concerns revolve around whether the reductions in manufacturing and consumption are necessary for a viable utilization of natural resources, contrasting sharply with the "green development" tale (Hinkel et al., 2020). The proponents of this narrative argue that the decline is the most realistic method for addressing the root causes of environmental damage since smaller countries consume fewer resources and emit fewer greenhouse gases. Furthermore, they argue that developed nations appear to be running out of strategies to sustain long-term economic growth, implying that decline is an alternative to consider (Raworth, 2017).

Degrowth is seldom considered at the international scale, and green growth remains the prevailing narrative for environmental sustainability in policy, whatever the reasons (Wiedmann *et al.* 2015). That happens because modern economies and power structures are strongly correlated with economic growth, casting doubts as to whether degrowth could result in the kind of extensive and urgent climate action currently required. Additionally, empirical data indicates that declining economic growth results in fewer jobs and an equitable society, with little data indicating how a widespread degrowth transition could be implemented without causing significant social disturbance (Kallis *et al.*, 2018). Ying's GREEN-WIN project's primary goal was to identify practical features and creative methods to conceptualize the environmental crisis to transcend the traditional arguments about sustainable development and decline. (Raworth, 2017; Hickel and Kallis, 2020).

The revolutionary Win-Win narratives (WWS)

The GREEN-WIN project's win-win narratives blend integrate the aspects of bottom-up, transformational narratives with a conservative variant of the sustainable development narrative. In addition to addressing climate and sustainability goals concurrently, they expand that WWS is financially appealing to personal businesses, some localities, and the entire economy, given their current actions. The study contends that these WWS are essential to moving climate action forward since most nations, companies, and people worldwide are unable or unwilling to forgo short-term economic growth in favor of carbon reductions (Hinkel *et al.*, 2020).

According to UNICEF 2019, 2.2 billion people have no access to safe drinking water worldwide, while 0.7 billion people live in severe poverty. The best way forward for such people and their countries is

socioeconomic prosperity. It is a bad idea for nations that might theoretically afford significant emission reductions to sacrifice economic growth (Thornton *et al.*, 2020). Continuing conversations among various countries show that recommendations for extensive abatement techniques have been dismissed just because they could damage businesses and cause loss of employment.

WWS is critical for eliminating the institutional, behavioral, psychological, financial, and other barriers that frequently prevent climate change adoption. That is another reason WWS is crucial to advancing climate action in the current period. It is essential to note that many of these challenges stem from financial and economic issues. For instance, even economically advantageous adaptation measures are frequently discouraged due to a lack of sustainable financing (Hinkel *et al.*, 2018). Senior decision makers in business and government frequently impede climate mitigation actions narrowly by focusing on short-term business concerns (Van Der Leeuw, 2020). Since WWS now yield economic benefits, they serve as a conduit for improving access to financing and incorporating climate change concerns into short-term decision-making. Institutional barriers can also be overcome by considering the various interests of all stakeholders.

Although win-win stories and WWS may not solve the climate change crisis, they help to change the conversation in the right direction and overcome the obstacles to climate action caused by tales of doom and terror. The implementation of WWS may work for some actors and sectors, while it may cause long-term detrimental consequences for other actors or sectors. Therefore, it is critical to study and adapt to global strategies. However, WWS may shift the warming debate from a “pessimistic cost and doom” to one with the potential to spur additional climate action with indirect economic benefits (Leonidas *et al.*, 2020; Thornton *et al.*, 2020).

Discussion

This section presents a quick summary of the literature. It also presents a synthesis of systematic reviews of rethinking climatic change narratives and exploring innovative paths toward a sustainable future. We identified these key findings, and they are as follows. A tactical story-building technique that incorporates long-term strategy.

Innovative Paths Towards a Sustainable Future

Leadership

There must be effective domestic and global leadership as a long-term strategy for climate action. The government must also tackle climate change by initiating projects to create a positive image of its commitment to climate action. Rather than complaining about people’s resistance to change, the government can lead by example and assist its citizens through education and support (Bushell *et al.*, 2016).

Since there is a lack of clarity and certainty over our course, businesses need the government’s leadership and direction to foster change. Since the authorities seek to establish public support for their programs, they must connect through language and in visuals, utilizing photos and media outlets, and mind images. Government activities must be transparent and public to motivate the citizens toward supporting the initiatives (Parry *et al.*, 2015). Lastly, the government must lead in addressing climate change. This constitutes a part of a "social contract," since people frequently view changing their behavior as a contract containing expectations for both parties: Individuals will have high hopes for governmental and institutional actions if they believe in changing their behavior (Bushell *et al.*, 2016).

Big Picture

People must understand the scope of the problem and our goals, while the objectives and the vision remain the primary focus. Because of this larger-picture orientation, some of the most compelling stories that propel environmental change may not center on climate change for few or all audiences, but instead, concentrate on co-benefits like energy security or health (Bushell *et al.*, 2015). Even in cases not included in the narrative, leaders should understand what is at risk.

Institutions

Currently, there is a lack of coordinated thinking and clear communication amongst the pertinent institutions worldwide. This could be a sign of the overabundance of relevant and significant institutions, such as the Committee on Climate Change (CCC), the Department of Transport, the Department for Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS), the Treasury, and DECC the Department of Energy and Climate Change, among others. On the other hand, it could also signify the need to have a single organization in charge of coordinating all these affairs. As the Conservative Party stated as much in 2010, the goal was to attain "strategic clarity" (Bremer and Meisch, 2017).

Take-action

Most importantly, people must begin crafting more effective strategies and create an effective story. Creating the ideal strategy and putting it into action is critical because failing to implement the strategies may cause uncertainties in the fight against climate change. A suggested procedure is given for creating a strategic story. Despite the inevitable, professionals can rectify, and lessons learned since global warming is a running timer that cannot be stopped or slowed. Climate action is about what we have to do, and how soon we must do it (Bushell *et al.*, 2015).

Climate Change Adaptation Narratives

The Change narrative incorporates elements of future considerations, climatic expertise, and story communications. One must acknowledge vulnerability by accepting that not all climate hazards can be avoided, but measures can be taken to minimize future impacts. Since climate change is a current problem that requires urgent solutions, temporal factors are crucial to adaptation, especially considering the ever-rising temperatures (Preston *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, when considering transformative acts for future forecasts, there must be intention to set and plan for expected social and environmental changes to validate future thinking (Moser, 2016).

Despite climate adaptation being the primary concern, spontaneous comments tend to focus on the causes and mitigation of the negative impact of ecological degradation. However, few mentioned the expected outcomes of the same. "Future Thinking" was anchored on references to a particular time by indicating the important changes and connections between the previous and the present. Generally, the replies were divided into four Changes in Climate (Coulter *et al.*, 2019).

Distant narrative: obstacles to climate mitigation strategy

Most people suggest that they hardly ever talk about climate change in social situations. The comparatively low level of participation in the "Environmental Change Resilience Tales" manifests that problems related to climate could be out of reach. As a result, inadequate information was disclosed to friends and family to help determine what modifications were required. Moreover, there was little incentive or chance to organize and implement adaptation actions due to the clear story of remoteness, something most common among the replies (Coulter *et al.*, 2019; Kok *et al.*, 2019).

Knowledge, Convenience Society, Disaster, Feelings, and Society were some of the important themes that showed up in the narratives of distance. For instance, the interaction of Convenience Society, and Passion determine the appropriate time to talk about adaptation. Even individuals involved in

environmental mitigation initiatives prevent damage by discussing changes while speaking in their community because they feel it demotivates discussions about climate change. Psychological separation may also be a recurrent obstacle to communicating and comprehending climate issues on a personal level (Coulter *et al.*, 2019; Bevan, 2020).

Security narrative: lower susceptibility does not mean invulnerability.

Climate data was covered in the “Vulnerability” narrative using precise, "What if" language (Pedde *et al.*, 2019). The resulting scenarios avoided assessing vulnerability as a changing target by providing clear planning points as opposed to intervals of uncertainty. As a result, vulnerability was evaluated using a variety of opposing "all or nothing" criteria. The criteria had common yet difficult natural dangers comparatively less concerning due to familiarity, and immeasurable threats from unexpected disruptions (Thomas *et al.*, 2019).

Vulnerability stories frequently touched on the themes of calamity, interruption, proof, comprehension, limits, and unanswered questions. For example, the interaction of issues with evidence, interpretation, and limitation influenced the perception of government as providing society with consistent protection and decreasing vulnerability. However, there was increasing vulnerability because it was unable to manage unknown risks through creative solutions (Coulter *et al.*, 2019).

Agency narrative: duty and assets for adapting

According to this narrative, there was a correlation between having the agency to adjust to change in climate and having the obligation to support a family, and community, and the root cause of anthropogenic climate change (Hickman *et al.*, 2021). Individuals who placed a high value on their agency in comparison to others acknowledged that they had social and economic advantages over people in local and foreign societies.

Action, benefits, Facilities, Coping, Normality, and Resource were the themes that frequently appeared in accounts of agency. For instance, when social support is insufficient to bring up necessary adaptation, discussions of action, normalcy, and coping strategies can all contribute to a disappointed sense of agency (Cianconi *et al.*, 2020). In response to worries about resources and infrastructure, agencies were frequently considered in the context of their capacity to manage storms, droughts, floods, and fires. This ability can be witnessed by using strong infrastructure, well-planned housing, and effective natural resource management. Certain people perceive agency in their capacity to relocate or postpone facing climatic dangers until they pass away (Cianconi *et al.*, 2020).

Change narrative: seeking for adaptation

In the context of change, those who intended to adjust acknowledged that it is necessary to get ready now for upcoming obstacles. On the other hand, there is no explicit outline of a mutually agreed-upon action plan. Stories of Change highlighted several important themes, such as acceptance, cooperation, cosmopolitanism, expression, present, and transformation (Christensen and Jansson, 2015). Drawing on themes of acceptance, present, and transformation, it was determined that significant transformation was highly unlikely throughout the twenty years. Accordingly, making drastic adjustments may also raise susceptibility. Therefore, people must be maladaptive, or it could be ineffective because any advantages may not be appreciated (Coulter *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusion

Conclusively, most literature on the traditional narratives of environmental degradation suggest that there is a link between climate change and language, communication, storytelling, and the reaction of the public in a variety of ways. The "Top-down doom and gloom narrative " is a threat to the fight against climate

change since it may lead to adverse outcomes for society. Due to the lack of proper leadership, inadequate policymaking, and media reluctance, there is weak communication of proper climate change strategies to the general public. This research focused on rethinking the traditional narrative, recreating and exploring an innovative and transformative pathway toward a sustainable future. Further research might narrow down the gaps by investigating different innovative pathways and transformative narrative outcomes. Ultimately, most assessments advocate for greater study to further comprehend and measure these innovative pathways. That will provide valuable insights into accepting these narratives despite the obstacles. It is important to unpack 'what', and how these obstacles affect these pathways and the general public.

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